

Learning Listening Comprehension and Vocabulary Skills in relation to Writing Performance of Elementary Learner

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Abstract:- The ability to listen and comprehend spoken language is essential in developing a learner's reading and writing skills. This study determined the listening comprehension, vocabulary skills, and the writing ability of elementary learners of Misamis University. A total of 160 learners served as respondents of the study. Learners were asked to answer the researcher-made questionnaires with 15 questions from the audio presentation on Listening Comprehension Skill. For the Vocabulary Skills, the learners were asked to answer ten (10) questions about the unfamiliar words taken from the story they listened to. While for writing skills, the learners were asked to write an essay or opinion about the story. The data were analyzed statistically using the *Mean, Standard Deviation, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and Stepwise Regression Analysis*. The study revealed that the learners' listening comprehension was fairly satisfactory, whereas the learners' vocabulary skills belong to the category of did not meet expectations. The overall writing performance was fair to the learners' listening comprehension influenced their writing performance as to organization, development, and content. Similarly, grammar, mechanics, and penmanship were associated with writing performance. The teaching of vocabulary has to be an interdisciplinary project, integrated with all subjects at every grade level. School heads have to include in the co-curricular plan of activities writing contests to encourage the learners to showcase their writing abilities

Keywords:- Comprehension, Listening, Skill, Vocabulary, Writing

I. INTRODUCTION

Listening comprehension encompasses the multiple processes involved in understanding and making sense of spoken language. Listening comprehension includes recognizing speech, sounds, getting the meaning of individual words, or understanding the syntax of sentences in which they are presented. Listening is a skill that is not naturally developed. A study revealed that students' critical difficulty in listening comprehension pays more attention to writing, reading, and vocabulary (Gilakjani & Sabouri, 2016). There are significant issues that address the impact of familiarity with the topics on listening comprehension and the extent to which certain English elements are likely to be affected (Othman & Vanathas, 2017).

In second language learning, study, and teaching, listening is ignored despite its significance (Ahmadi, 2016). Repeated emphasis has been placed on the role of listening to understanding in language teaching because many educators do not pay sufficient attention to its significance in their courses (Gilakjani & Sabouri, 2016). In research conducted with 151 non-English primary learners at University in Northwest China, they investigated a high percentage of the variance in listening comprehension. It was explained by overall language skills, vocabulary size, and metacognitive consciousness (Gilakjani & Sabouri, 2016).

Second language incidental video vocabulary learning has focused primarily on short genre clips that can be beneficial to vocabulary teaching (Rodgers & Webb, 2019). Some researchers said that students remembered words better than when spellings when seen than not seen during learning and on delayed posttests. Students who decoded spellings learned pronunciation and meanings better during the learning trials compared to students who only viewed spellings, but the advantage of decoding declined one and a week (Chambrière, Ehri, & Ness, 2019). Prior knowledge of vocabulary can substantially impact the amount of vocabulary learning accomplished by extensive reading (Webb, & Chang, 2015). However, learners' also need to know the language, so to speak, not just in terms of learning a first or second language, but also in terms of learning the vocabulary that characterizes some other fields of study, such as biology or the law (Bjork, & Kroll, 2015).

Writing skill is considered, by many people, the most difficult skill to be mastered. Errors and mistakes in writing are unavoidable, and many of them have been detected with various types (Thao & Anh, 2017). The impact on student writing enhancement confirms the disadvantage of free Automated Writing Evaluation instruments in improving the skill (Parra, 2019).

Writing skill is more important to use for evaluation in terms of academic achievements. There are some studies on more effective pedagogy than the conventional lecture method for improving English writing skills (Dastgeer & Afzal, 2015). Teaching writing can take some measures to help students learn how to improve learners writing skills (Bagheri & Riasati, 2015). However, writing in English Foreign Language (EFL) classes as a strong skill is exceptionally important. There needs to be a positive partnership between the teacher and students in writing classes. As the only audience in many writing classes, the teacher reacts to the students (Shams-Abadi, Ahmadi, & Mehrdad, 2015).

Accumulated motivational control awareness is a backdrop to the documented use of other Self-regulated learners (SRL) techniques to affect the quality of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) writing. The use of Self-Regulated Learner approaches in the negotiation framework also leads to a clear understanding of (L2) writing processes in the SRL system. It enhances the quality of writing (Teng & Zhang, 2018). Most people find writing skills to be the most challenging ability to master in English learning. Besides, written errors and errors are unavoidable, and a large number of them with a variety of types have been found (Thao & Anh, 2017). In the study of Saudi, Mind mapping techniques were used to enhance the English Foreign Language learners' writing ability. It is a traditional technique for teaching intermediate learners and identifies appropriate application procedures to enhance writing skills (Bukhari, 2016).

Several studies on listening comprehension have been conducted; however, only a few are related to the learners' vocabulary and writing performance. Moreover, the learners

nowadays are lacked interest in listening, since they do not consider listening important. In Misamis University, teachers in Basic Education Department often complain that their learners have inadequate listening and writing skills. This study is conducted to find out the extent to which the linguistic variables of listening comprehension and vocabulary influence the learners' writing performance.

II. METHOD

The respondents of this study were 160 elementary pupils of Misamis University, Philippines selected through purposive sampling. They took the Listening Comprehension, Vocabulary, and Writing Skills Test within the span of the study.

The data were collected and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Hence, this study is a descriptive-correlational study.

III. FINDINGS

A. Learner's Listening Comprehension

Table 1 presents the data on the learners' listening comprehension. The data revealed that the learners' listening comprehension was reasonably satisfactory (M= 10.09; SD = 4.07). This means that the learners lacked the listening comprehension skills needed at their level.

Table 1. Learner's Listening Comprehension Skills

Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding (13-15)	35	21.74
Very Satisfactory (12)	56	34.78
Satisfactory (11)	47	29.19
Fairly Satisfactory (9-10)	22	13.66
Did not Meet Expectations (8 and below)	1	0.62
Mean	10.09 –Fairly Satisfactory	

Note :Scale: 13-15 (Outstanding); 12 (Very Satisfactory); 11 (Satisfactory); 9-10 (Fairly Satisfactory); 8 and below (Did not Meet Expectations)

B. Learner's Vocabulary Skills

Table 2 presents the data on the learners' vocabulary skills. The data revealed that learners' vocabulary skills "did not meet expectations" set in the subject (M= 3.58; SD = 2.52). This means that learners do not yet have the vocabulary skill. The learners experienced difficulty in understanding some terms or difficult words from the selection provided by the teacher from English textbooks. Their ability to define or identify the meaning of the words presented to them was not fully developed.

Table 2. Learner's Vocabulary Skills

Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding (9-10)	0	0.00
Very Satisfactory (8)	0	0.00
Satisfactory (7)	0	0.00
Fairly Satisfactory (6)	30	18.63
Did not Meet Expectations (5 - below)	131	81.37
Mean	3.58 – Did not Meet Expectations	

Note :Scale: 9-10 (Outstanding); 8 (Very Satisfactory); 7 (Satisfactory); 6 (Fairly Satisfactory); 5 and below (Did not Meet Expectations)

C. Learner's Writing Performance

Table 3 presents the data on the learners' writing performance. The data revealed that learners' writing performance was fair ($M=2.29$; $SD 1.11$). This means that learners can only write fairly. They still have to learn to present ideas clearly and to support with details. They still need to organize thoughts and write ideas with an inviting introduction. Moreover, learners have to make sure that all the details they write support the main topic, and provide an overview and information in a logical order.

Table 3. Learner's Writing Performance

Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Very Satisfactory (3.25-4.0)	37	22.98
Satisfactory (2.50 – 3.24)	36	22.36
Fair (1.75 – 2.49)	36	22.36
Poor (1.0-1.74)	52	32.30
Overall Writing Performance	2.29 – Fair	

Note: Scale: 3.25-4.0 (*Very Satisfactory*); 2.50-3.24 (*Satisfactory*); 1.75-2.49 (*Fair*) 1.0-1.74 (*Poor*)

D. Significant Relationship between Learners' Listening Comprehension and Writing Performance

The test of the significant relationship between learners' listening comprehension and writing performance is shown in Table 4. A highly significant relationship was noted between learners' listening comprehension and the learners' writing performance in the skills of content, grammar and mechanics, and penmanship. However, a significant relationship between the learners' listening comprehension and learners' writing performance in organization and development was seen.

Table 4. Significant Relationship between Learners' Listening Comprehension and Writing Performance

Variables	r-value	p-value	Remarks
Listening Comprehension and:			
Organization	0.18*	0.02	Significant
Content	0.24**	0.00	Highly Significant
Development	0.19*	0.02	Significant
Grammar & Mechanics	0.23**	0.00	Highly Significant
Penmanship	0.21*	0.01	Highly Significant

Note: ** means highly significant at .01 level; * means significant at 0.05 level

E. Significant Relationship between the Learners' Vocabulary Skills and Writing Performance

The test of the significant relationship between learners' vocabulary skills and writing performance is shown in Table 5. A highly significant relationship is noted between learners' vocabulary skills and writing performance with p-values less than or equal to zero (0.00). This means that vocabulary skills are prerequisite to writing skills. One has difficulty in writing if he lacks vocabulary.

Table 5. Significant Relationship between Learners' Vocabulary Skills and Writing Performance

Variables	r-value	p-value	Remarks
Vocabulary Skills and:			
Organization	0.23	0.00	Highly Significant
Content	0.22	0.00	Highly Significant
Development	0.25	0.00	Highly Significant
Grammar & Mechanics	0.22	0.01	Highly Significant
Penmanship	0.21	0.01	Highly Significant

Note: ** means highly significant at .01 level

F. Predictors of Learners' Writing Performance

Table 6 revealed that the two independent variables, listening comprehension ($\beta=0.05$; $t=2.46$, $p=0.02$) and vocabulary skills ($\beta=0.09$; $t=2.62$, $p=0.01$) predicted the learners' writing skills. The regression equation (Writing Performance = $1.48 + 0.05$ Listening + 0.08 Vocabulary) indicates that the increase of the sum of listening and vocabulary of learners by a unit, the learners' writing performance will also increase. The variation of learners' writing skills is explained by the sum of listening comprehension skills and vocabulary for 88 percent ($r^2 = 88$). This means that 88 percent of the learners' writing skill is attributed to listening comprehension and vocabulary development, while the remaining 22 percent is attributed by other factors which are not included in the study.

Table 6. Predictors of Learners' Writing Performance

Predictors	Coef (β)	SE Coef	T- Value	P-Value
(Constant)	1.48	0.24	6.32	0.00
1. Listening Comprehension	0.05	0.02	2.46*	0.02
2. Vocabulary Skills	0.09	0.03	2.62**	0.01
$R^2 = 89\%$				
Dependent Variable: Writing Performance				
Writing Performance = 1.48 + 0.05 Listening + 0.08 Vocabulary				

Note: * means p -value ≤ 0.05 ; significant

IV. DISCUSSIONS

Listening comprehension is the least visible process in second language teaching and learning. Teachers find it challenging to teach listening and listening activities used in language classrooms (Goh, 2018). Language learners have significant problems in listening because schools pay more attention to structure, writing, reading, and vocabulary (MA & MA, 2014). When teachers are aware of learners' learning difficulties, they can help them develop effective listening strategies and finally solve their difficulties in listening and improve their listening comprehension abilities (Gilakjani & Sabouri, 2016).

Teachers have to do often listening to classroom activities since most of the time, teachers focus on writing and speaking. Listening is part of the macro skills that should be taught and developed to children as this will help the learners develop their communication skills. Factors like physical disability or even lack of facilities in the classroom have to be taken into consideration.

The learners achieved satisfactory listening comprehension because of the following factors: learners were not interested in listening, paid more attention to reading with visual, and through it, they can easily understand the story or the selection. Since the learners are now in the 21st century, most of them are more engaged in gadgets, multimedia, and other social media. The writing performance of learners in terms of content, grammar, and mechanics, and penmanship was highly affected by the listening comprehension skills. Also, writing organization and development was significantly influenced by the learners' listening comprehension. The increase in learners' performance in listening comprehension will cause an increase of their performance in writing.

On the other hand, the factor why the learners did not meet expectations in their vocabulary skills is because they do not pay attention to listening to the story or the audio presentation, which made them experienced difficulty in answering the test. The words used in vocabulary skills were taken from the story; this implies that the learners were more interested in visual presentation than on audio presentation.

Teachers need to focus their activities on developing the vocabulary skills of the learners. The learners may be given seatwork activity wherein the teacher writes some unfamiliar words on the board and asks them to construct sentences using these words. Learners also may be given a chance to use their cellphone to play word escape games for ten (10)

minutes. While playing, the learners should note or write the unfamiliar word that they encounter during the game and later find their meanings. Also, Bookworm game is advised for the learners wherein they form words based on the given letters, they are going to take note of the unfamiliar words that they encounter during the game, and after the time given by the teacher, the learners are required to construct sentences through it.

Teachers in the classroom have to start their lessons through unlocking difficult words before presenting the texts like story or poem to be read. A thorough understanding of learners in the vocabulary has to be ensured. Using different techniques in learning English vocabulary is of great help. These include listening for context clues, using a dictionary, singing a song, drawing a picture, using flashcards, playing vocabulary games, and downloading language apps.

The study revealed that prior knowledge of vocabulary can have a substantial impact on the amount of vocabulary learning accomplished by extensive reading, thus contributing to the learners' writing ability (Webb & Chang, 2015). The main and interaction effects were the contribution of vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension. Results of correlation analysis suggested that comprehension, vocabulary, and reading were significantly related to the text description of the writing skills (Nurdiani & Abdurahman, 2018).

Writing is an opportunity to enhance and consolidate vocabulary, and vocabulary is one of the most important features of writing. Hence, teachers need to develop first the vocabulary skills of learners before they can expect a good output in writing. Teachers have to offer direct instruction of techniques or procedures for developing a broad and varied vocabulary. This instruction can be through various classroom interactions-such as story time-with learners. The teaching of vocabulary has to be an interdisciplinary project, integrated into the curriculum at every level.

Writing the essay properly and correctly the learners should listen very well to the audio presentation. If the learners comprehend the story, can answer the questions based on the story from the presentation, they can answer the questions based on the story they heard. In this study, the learners in grade 3 & 4 were not familiar with the story given by the researcher so the learners really tried their best to listen to the story but still they failed in answering the vocabulary activity. If the learners lack understanding, the learners also experience difficulty in writing. For Grades 5 & 6 there were

learners who were good in writing an essay but most of the Grades 5 and 6 learners experienced difficulty in grammar, and organization of ideas. However, the activity teaches learners to improve their penmanship.

Writing is an important skill in language production. However, it is considered a difficult skill, particularly in English as a second language (ESL) context where learners face many challenges in writing (Fareed, Ashraf, & Bilal, 2016). It is well established that the activity of producing a text is a complex one involving three main cognitive processes: planning, translating, and revising. Although these processes are crucial in skilled writing, beginning and developing writers seem to struggle with them, mainly with planning and revising (Limpo, Alves, & Fidalgo, 2014). Learners who used Google Docs apps have improved their writing ability than those who did not (Suwantarathip & Wichadee, 2014).

With the emergence of technology today, the attention of learner is shifted to gadgets. Thus, writing ability is sacrificed. With this, teachers need to be vigilant enough that they match the strategy they use in the classroom with their learners' learning styles. Allowing learners to use online apps in their writing activity may help develop their writing skills and ability. Of course, the role of technology cannot replace the role of a traditional teacher. Hence, teachers have to give daily writing activities. Also, teachers have to make sure that they check all the writing performances of learners even during quizzes to practice the skills of writing like content organization and development, grammar and mechanics, and penmanship.

Vocabulary and syntactic and phonological awareness were all important to the overall writing ability of the learners (Harrison, et al., 2016). Spelling, grammar, and punctuation jointly predict written composition achievement with spelling as the main predictor.

Instructions on listening comprehension have an integral part of writing instruction. Instructions on these components may be incorporated into activities like book reading or reading comprehension instructions. As teachers develop lesson plans in a language classroom, it is crucial to ensure that students practice all language elements. With each activity, teachers need to consider how to incorporate multiple skills— such as listening and writing — to enhance language mastery. Just like a basketball player who excels in dribbling, passing through defense and shooting, a student needs to gain speaking, reading, writing, and listening skills to become an all-star in language.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that teachers use listening activities to develop the learners' comprehension. Encourage the learners to often listen some English story to practice their skill in listening. The School Head may also should provide facilities that is used for listening activities such as smart TV in each classroom to help provide equipment that teacher's may use

for authentic activities in as much as most learners these days are more engaged in technology rather than listening to their teacher always speaking or discussing in the class. Some of these authentic listening activities would be dictation taking, watching movies for listening comprehension and some simple listening word completion exercises.

The teaching of vocabulary has to be an interdisciplinary project, integrated into the curriculum at every grade level. By providing activities related to vocabulary such as playing wordscape, Bookworm and the Scrabble, learners are allowed to use their cellphones. The teacher will ask the learners to do the activity by answering the wordscape, bookworm and scrabble game and ask them to take note of the unfamiliar word they encounter during the game. The activity should be done one at a time. School heads have to include in the co-curricular plan of activities writing contests to encourage the learners to showcase their writing abilities. Future researchers may also conduct another research that provides intervention to learners with very poor vocabulary and writing skills.

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